

Mindfulness in Arts & Science P.G Students of Karnatak University, Dharwad

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Abstract: Mindfulness is the mental state that involves being fully focused on the “now.” It is an acceptance of our thoughts, feelings and sensations without judgement. This study aimed to understand and analyze mindfulness of post-graduation students of arts and science background and also to identify the effect of the demographic variables on the mindfulness. To study the same, total sample of 120 Science and Arts students consisting of male and female samples were included in the study. To measure their mindfulness levels constructed by Ryan Brown and Fred Bryant respectively were administered for the subjects. For the obtained raw score, mean and SD was calculated in each groups. Later independent ‘t’ test was carried out to find the difference between the comparative groups. The main finding of the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between arts and science students on mindfulness. But, there is significant difference in mindfulness between Arts male and Science male students. Science male students have high mindfulness than Arts male students.

Keywords: Mindfulness, Awareness, Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction, Non-judgement, Thoughts, Positive Psychology, Present moment, Mindful Meditation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mindfulness is a moment-to-moment awareness of one’s experience without judgment. In this sense, mindfulness is a state and not a trait. While it might be promoted by certain practices or activities, such as meditation, it is not equivalent to or synonymous with them. (APA, 2012). It is the awareness that arises from paying attention, on purpose, in the present moment and non-judgmentally (Jon Kabat Zinn). Mindfulness is also the practice of maintaining a non-judgmental state of heightened or complete awareness of one’s thoughts, emotions, or experiences on a moment-to-moment basis. It is the practice of being aware of your body, mind, and feelings in the present moment, thought to create a feeling of calm.

Mindfulness has been a part of the positive psychology world for years and a popular topic in the broader field before that it actually predates the modern field of psychology. Dr. Jon Kabat-Zinn is considered the “founding father” of the U.S.-based mindfulness trend. He was introduced to mindfulness through his exploration of Buddhist philosophy in his college days, which he then incorporated into his practice as a professor of medicine at the University of Massachusetts Medical School. He founded the Stress Reduction Clinic at the UM medical school in 1979, where he developed the program that is known today as Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) (Shea, 2018). Since then, mindfulness has grown in popularity and is increasingly the subject of studies on ways to reduce stress, increase positivity, and increase quality of life.

Mindfulness is an excellent way to practice self-care, which makes it a great tool that helping professionals can share with their clients to encourage healing, growth, and healthy habits outside of the one-hour office visits. To teach clients about mindfulness, we can describe and walk them through some of the exercises from mindfulness expert Jon Kabat-Zinn. Some of the mindfulness exercises are mindful breathing, body scan meditation, raisin meditation, walking meditation, loving-kindness meditation. If a client asks for a recommendation on how long or how frequently they should practice mindfulness, we can tell them there’s no harm in practicing as often as they’d like, but that committing to even the shortest of practices

(e.g., 5 minutes a day) can have significant impacts on their life. According to Richie Davidson, one of the world's most renowned contemplative neuroscientists, even 1.5 hours of mindfulness practice can lead to positive structural changes in the brain.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Atefeh Ahmadi et al., (2014) conducted research on mindfulness and related factors among undergraduate Students. The purpose of this research was to investigate the status of mindfulness among students. 273 undergraduate students studying in the first semester were research participants. This study was carried out using Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale. The mean score of mindfulness in the respondents is 3.77 and there was no significant correlation between the level of mindfulness and age, gender, religion, race, family and educational background. The correlation was between the level of mindfulness and health condition ($\alpha=.04$, 2 tailed). To strengthen the level of mindfulness among students, increasing health condition, upgrading the quality of mental health, applying mindful principles and increasing thrust and novelty in universities are beneficial.

Dunning et al., (2018) conducted a meta-analysis examining the behavioral, cognitive, and mental health outcomes for students following a mindfulness intervention. Their results demonstrated significant positive effects of mindfulness-based interventions for outcomes of mindfulness, executive functioning, attention, depression, anxiety, stress, and maladaptive behaviors. Flett et al. (2020) studied the impact of an app-based mindfulness meditation upon psychological distress and college adjustment in incoming university students. Their findings demonstrated that participants who used the app more frequently reported improvements in psychological distress and college adjustment. These findings are particularly relevant to the present study as they suggest in-person mindfulness interventions delivered at the beginning of the academic year for first-year students may encourage uptake and retention.

Van Vugt and Jha (2011) undertook research that involved taking a group of participants to an intensive month-long mindfulness retreat. These participants were compared with a control group who received no mindfulness training (MT). All participants from both groups first undertook a memory recognition task before any MT had been providing. The second round of a memory recognition task was then undertaken by all participants after the month's training. These results suggested that MT leads to attention improvements, particularly in relation to quality of information and decisional processes, which are directly linked to working memory.

A self-report study conducted at the University of North Carolina by Brown Iannuzzi, Adair, Payne, Richman, and Fredrickson (2014) measured the level of discrimination experienced by participants as well as the presence and if present severity of their depressive symptoms. The results showed that, as expected, the more discrimination participants experienced the more depressive symptoms they had. It was also found that the more mindful people were the less depressed they were. Finally, and most importantly, the findings suggested that mindfulness might be a protective factor that mitigates the effects of discrimination on the development of depressive symptoms.

3. METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To investigate whether Arts and Science Post-Graduate students differ significantly in Mindfulness.
- To assess Male and Female Post-Graduate students differ significantly in Mindfulness.

Hypothesis:

- There will be significant difference between Arts and Science PG students in their Mindfulness.
- There will be significant difference between Male and Female PG students in their Mindfulness.

Variables:

1. Independent Variable: Science and Arts stream of education
2. Dependent Variable: Mindfulness

Sample:

In order to examine the above-mentioned hypotheses, a total sample of 120 post-graduate students from Arts (60) and Science (60) faculty were selected from Karnatak University, Dharwad. The sample from each faculty consists of 30 male and 30 female PG students. The age range of sample is 21 to 25. Purposive sampling method was adopted to select the sample.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The students included were of the age group of 21 to 25.
2. PG students were included from only arts and science faculty.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. The students below the age group of 21 and above the age group of 25 were not included as the sample for study.
2. Other faculty apart from arts and science were not included.

Measures Used:

1. Mindfulness Scale: The Mindfulness Attention Awareness Scale was used to measure Mindfulness of the subjects. A self-report measure designed to assess a core characteristic of mindfulness. The scale consists of 15 items. There are 6 responses- not at all true (1) almost always, (2) very frequently, (3) Somewhat frequently, (4) Somewhat infrequently, (5) Very infrequently and (6) Almost never. The total score is calculated by finding the sum of all items. For the MAAS, the total score ranges between 15 and 90, with higher scores indicating more mindfulness. Cronbach's alpha for the whole MAAS is .92. Corrected item-total correlations of the MAAS ranged from .46 to .74. Validity: MAAS are correlated with other psychometrically sound measures of mindfulness (r with Freiburg Mindfulness Inventory = .31, $p < .01$; r with Kentucky Inventory of Mindfulness Skills = .51, $p < .01$; r with Cognitive Affective Mindfulness Scale = .51, $p < .01$; r with Mindfulness Questionnaire = .38; $p < .01$).

Statistical Techniques Applied:

- Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD)
- 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between male and female PG students.

4. RESULTS

Table 01: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts and Science students on Mindfulness

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts students (60)	Science students (60)		
Mindfulness	Mean	48.36	51.64	1.814	.072
	SD	11.14	8.49		

Table 02: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and science male students on Mindfulness

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts male students (30)	Science male students (30)		
Mindfulness	Mean	47.94	52.98	1.95*	.058
	SD	12.21	7.23		

Table 03: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts female and science female students on Mindfulness.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts female students (30)	Science female students (30)		
Mindfulness	Mean	48.78	50.30	0.60	.552
	SD	10.16	9.51		

Table 04: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and female students on Mindfulness.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts male students (30)	Arts female students (30)		
Mindfulness	Mean	47.94	48.78	-0.29	.772
	SD	12.21	10.16		

Table 05: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Science male and female students on Mindfulness.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Science male students (30)	Science female students (30)		
Mindfulness	Mean	52.98	50.30	1.23	.225
	SD	7.23	9.51		

5. DISCUSSION

Data was collected from PG Arts and Science students studying in Karnatak University, Dharwad. With a permission of the chairperson the students were contacted and a good rapport was established. After introducing the study to the students, their consent was sought and the research was carried out assuring confidentiality. Socio-demographic information was collected and then the above-mentioned measures were administered with appropriate instructions. The forms were collected after the completion of all the scales. Statistical techniques were applied in the study using Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD) and 't' test. 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between male and female PG students.

Table 01 from results depicts Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts and Science students on Mindfulness. The Mean score obtained by the Science students on Mindfulness is 51.64 and Arts students is 48.36. The obtained 't' value for the difference is 1.81, which is not significant. This reveals that there is no significant differences in mindfulness between Arts and Science students. Table 02 shows that Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and Science male students on Mindfulness. The Mean score obtained by the Science male students on Mindfulness is 52.98 and Arts male students is 47.94. The obtained 't' value for the difference is 1.95, which is significant at 0.058. This reveals that there is significant differences in mindfulness between Arts male and Science male students. In table 03, The Mean score obtained by the Science female students on Mindfulness is 50.30 and Arts female students is 48.78. The obtained 't' value for the difference is 0.60, which is not significant. This reveals that there is no significant difference in mindfulness between Arts female and Science female students.

Table 04 describes Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and Arts female students on Mindfulness. The Mean score obtained by the Arts female students on Mindfulness is 48.78 and Arts male students is 47.94. The obtained 't' value for the difference is 0.29, which is not significant. This reveals that there are no significant differences in mindfulness between Arts male and Arts female students. In table 05, there are Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Science male and Science female students on Mindfulness. The Mean score obtained by the Science male students on Mindfulness is 52.98 and Science female students is 50.30. The obtained 't' value for the difference is 1.23, which is not significant. This reveals that there is no significant difference in mindfulness between Science male and Science female students.

6. CONCLUSION

The main finding of the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between arts and science students on mindfulness.

- The findings reveal there is no significant difference in mindfulness between Arts and Science students.
- There is significant difference in mindfulness between Arts male and Science male students. Science male students have high mindfulness than Arts male students.
- There is no significant difference in mindfulness between Arts female and Science female students.
- There is no significant difference in mindfulness between Arts male and Arts female students.
- There is no significant difference in mindfulness between Science male and Science female students.

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size in the main group and sub groups are smaller. The result cannot be generalized.
- Other socio-demographic variables were not taken into consideration in the study, they may have implications on the dependent variables.
- The tools were not administered individually, which may lead to errors in the responses given by the subjects.
- The study consists of only two variables, which may be inadequate for a research.

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